

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Oxus Society for Central Asian Affairs (2020): Central Asia Protest Tracker (CAPT) (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/5BDAEC8F-82DF-46B6-8259-CE6BF55E2EE6>

Abstract

The Oxus Society for Central Asian Affairs compiled an original dataset that describes and categorizes protest events in the form of an interactive map, while covering variables such as protest types, issues, target types and responses. It contains a collection of all protest data published online in the following areas: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. The research team decided to define a protest as follows: “A protest action is a public expression of objection towards an idea or action of an individual or institution, including state organs, businesses, organizations and foreign governments which happens in physical space.” (2: 2). In total the data collection contains 2.500+ instances of coded protests. Some countries are however more extensively covered than others. As of summer 2024, work on the data collection seems to be continuing. The data review contains a link to the Central Asia Protest Tracker Website, where all relevant materials such as the Central Asia Protest Tracker Codebook, the full dataset and more are available as a free download.

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Data Review - Central Asia Protest Tracker

The Oxus Society for Central Asian Affairs compiled an original dataset that describes and categorizes protest events in the form of an interactive map. It contains a collection of all protest data published online in the following areas: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan (1). The research team decided to define a protest as follows: *“A protest action is a public expression of objection towards an idea or action of an individual or institution, including state organs, businesses, organizations and foreign governments which happens in physical space.”* (2: 2).

The process of data collection began using an online keyword search to identify protests fitting the above mentioned criteria. The database consists of publically available data sources, such as local language news media and supplementary evidence from social media in the form of photographic and video images (2: 3). Thus, it allows for cross-checks, verification and follow-up studies by independent analysts (2: 1). After a protest that fits the criteria was found, the research team ensured the validity of the information via local language media reports. If the reports contained scarce details on specifics, additional searches on social media were conducted in order to acquire more information (2: 4). While researching, vague terms to describe both the number of participants and arrests were common. So the research team had to decide on a way to classify terms such as “several” and “dozens” in a scientific manner: *“In such cases, we have chosen to use a multiple of three to provide a conservative assessment. In other words, “hundreds” would be coded as “300,” while “dozens” is listed as “36.” For presented ranges, e.g. “20-30 protesters,” we chose to always code according to the lower end estimate.”* (2: 7). To supplement the keyword search, data conforming to the above-mentioned definition of a ‘protest’, found in the Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project ([ACLED \(Armed Conflict Location and Event Data\) \(acleddata.com\)](https://acleddata.com)) was utilised (2: 4).

While coding every reported protest was included, meaning that some entries consist of just one protester. Ongoing protests which lasted for longer than a day or spanned multiple locations on the same day were counted as separate instances (2: 2). The collected data contains ten types of political protests, 28 categories of issues taken up by activists, ten forms of response by state actors, and nine types of targets being singled out by demonstrators. A full list of all recorded variables such as types, issues, target types and responses can be found in *The Central Asia Protest Tracker Codebook* (2: 5-6). On top of the aspects mentioned above, the research includes both a brief description of the events that took place in the listed protest, as well as the original source from which the information was acquired. The original sources however, are written mostly in Russian and, besides English, include other languages such as Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Uzbek and Tajik (2: 3).

Because of the manner in which data was gathered, there is no way to exclude the possibility that some cases of activism which may not have been ‘newsworthy’ enough or took place in

remote areas and were thus not covered by the media, may not be included in this dataset (2: 2). This issue might account for some of the discrepancies between the accounted protest cases of the Kyrgyz ministry in 2018 (552) and those confirmed in this dataset (107) (2: 3). Thus, the Oxus Society states: *“Academics and analysts using the database should be aware that this dataset is by no means comprehensive but is intended to demonstrate patterns of contentious politics throughout the region.”* (2: 2).

The database is being reviewed and updated on a regular basis. While currently a time period of about two and half years is covered, the Oxus Society intends to expand the data historically while also continuing to monitor and code future protests (2: 1).

Country coverage:

Country	Number of Entries
Kazakhstan	1329
Kyrgyzstan	889
Tajikistan	267
Turkmenistan	31
Uzbekistan	20
Total Entries	2536

Sources:

- (1) Central Asia Protest Tracker. <https://oxussociety.org/viz/protest-tracker/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (2) The Oxus Society of Central Asian Affairs. Central Asia Protest Tracker Codebook. <https://oxussociety.org/viz/protest-tracker/data/CAPT%20Code%20Book.pdf>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.